

25 March 2024

Press release

The CST4ALL project successfully held the online “Industry Workshop on the hybridisation of Concentrated Solar Thermal Technologies (CST) with PV” on 22 February 2024. This virtual event, organised by ESTELA with the collaboration of all CST4ALL partners and the support of the European Technology and Innovation Platform for Photovoltaics (ETIP PV), brought together over 140 stakeholders from the energy sector across 20 countries in Europe and beyond.

The workshop aimed to assess the industrial potential of concepts involving PV technologies coupled with parts of the CST value chain.

Dr. Konstantinos Genikomsakis from ESTELA opened the event by welcoming the attendees and introduced the CST4ALL project and the workshop objectives and agenda, followed by an overview of the EU policy landscape by Elisabeth Schellmann from the European Commission.

The workshop featured keynote presentations by renowned experts, namely Univ. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Robert Pitz-Paal (DLR Institute of Solar Research) from ESTELA and Eero Vartiainen (Fortum Renewables) and Dr. Peter Fath (RCT Solutions) from ETIP PV, providing insights on CST-PV hybrid concepts, market landscape and dynamics, and potential opportunities for hybridisation.

These presentations set the stage for engaging roundtable discussions moderated by Dr. Joachim Krüger (Solarlite CSP Technology GmbH and President of ESTELA) and Thomas Garabetian (Solar Power Europe). The discussions delved deeper into the industrial readiness of these technologies, project financing considerations, and the potential synergies between the CST and PV sectors in research and development, manufacturing, market development, and workforce training.

The workshop attracted a broad range of stakeholders, including representatives from the European Commission, national authorities, industry, research institutions and universities. This diverse audience participated in interactive live polls and was invited to contribute to a public opinion survey on Green Deal challenges & social sciences and humanities (SSH) and gender aspects.

Dr. Peter Heller, coordinator of the CST4ALL project, concluded the event by summarising key insights and takeaways. One of the key outcomes of the event is the recognition that these technologies are not in competition, but rather complement each other. Their hybridisation can combine their strengths, resulting in lower levelised cost of energy (LCOE) and higher capacity factors compared to single, independent plants.

**Funded by
the European Union**

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This CST4ALL project event was organised with the support of ETIP PV - The European Technology & Innovation Platform for Photovoltaics.

CST4ALL Coordinator

**Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.**
in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas,
Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

The CST4ALL project is committed to catalysing an array of hybridisation and cooperation initiatives at the interface between CST and other renewable energy technologies targeting the electricity, heat, and fuels sectors.

To stay up-to-date on CST4ALL's activities and opportunities, follow-us on:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cst4all/>
- X (formerly Twitter): <https://twitter.com/Cst4All>
- Website: <https://cst4all.eu/en/>

You can also sign-up for the **CST4ALL Newsletter** to receive updates on other project events and outputs through the following link: <https://cst4all.eu/en/4169-contact-connect>.

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